

Politics, Education, and Understanding: Anglo-American Readings and Misreadings of Rousseau in the 19th to 21st Centuries

Guillemette Johnston

In Anglo-American academia and culture generally, there is often a tendency to support and reflect extant ideological positions, to maintain a brand of conformism across the board. As might be expected in any ideological model that tries to justify the status quo, controversial figures and ideas are portrayed according to dominant ideological conceptions — conceptions that aim to support and promote the dominant social order. We can see a prime example of this happening with readings of Jean-Jacques Rousseau that appear in America in the late-19th through the 20th centuries, particularly in the post-World War Two era, as America emerged as a dominant world force standing in opposition to the Soviet Union in the Cold War period. After reviewing Rousseau's reception in America in the 19th century, we will look at various twentieth-century Anglo-American readings of Rousseau, with much focus on the period following the Second World War. In doing so we will examine the reasons Rousseau's philosophy came to be viewed as a source for the extinction of traditional Judeo-Christian moral values, leading to the creation of twentieth-century totalitarian regimes. To this end we will provide commentary on the misperception of key concepts in Rousseau's writings in the ideological readings provided by Babbitt, Talmon, and Crocker. After this survey we will look at contemporary writers whose misconceptions regarding Rousseau's philosophy demonstrate a limited understanding of Rousseau's works, or whose comments point to propagandistic usurpations of Rousseau's intentions, as for instance in the work of the contemporary Christian conservative Michael Coffman. We will thus show how Rousseau has been received in the Anglo-American world, and how his writings, particularly those concerning politics but also those that address the relationship of politics to education, have served as a lightning rod for ideological positions and causes. This approach will highlight deficiencies in academic readings of the period due to the hard-core political positions taken by some, but not all, of the scholars and academics of the time, and point to incapacities on behalf of some scholars and critics to read Rousseau with a genuine empathy for the stylistic flourishes and idiosyncrasies displayed by this idealistic autodidact. Thus we will demonstrate how for the academic reader and in academic circles in general, Rousseau's texts often serve as a canvas or screen for the portrayal and projection of ideological fantasies. Let it be said that often, as a result of these projections, Rousseau is read not for what he says but for what the particular critic reading him wishes to prove with respect to Anglo-American or contemporary society, sometimes at the cost of accuracy. At base this study then questions systems of reading, pointing toward ways ideology impacts interpretation of

important philosophical thinkers and figures, a fact that in turn has a profound effect on the presentation of these philosophers and their ideas in culture and in the educational system.

Rousseau was held in relatively high esteem in 18th and 19th century America, according to Frederick William Dame.¹ Dame argues that Rousseau had a significant effect on American literature and thought, either directly (for example, the poet Philip Freneau, one of the Connecticut Wits of the late 18th century, translated Rousseau) or indirectly, through the German Idealism of Kant or other writers and philosophers whose work was influenced by Rousseau. Thus in much of American intellectual life before the twentieth century we find profound appreciation for and acceptance of Rousseauist ideas. As Dame points out, depictions of nature were essentially benevolent (Emerson and Thoreau stand out here), the « *homme de la nature* » was presented in idealized portraits like those of native Americans or frontiersmen found in the novels of James Fenimore Cooper, and general Romanticist tendencies led many to believe that humanity was inherently good. While it would be inaccurate to say that these perceptions dominated all of American cultural life, Dame at least sees behind them the philosophical possibilities raised by Rousseau's works. Here are his comments regarding the importance of Rousseau as a force in American society:

The Romantic vision of Rousseau persevered not only in regard to the themes of literature, such as portrayals of the “noble savage” and man progressing and developing through his physical experiences and the senses, but also in the concept of the individual who must prove himself to himself before seeking to enter or re-enter the social state. He provided the foundation upon which the American Transcendentalists would build a philosophical as well as a literary movement. In the vision of man as innately good and reasonable, or man as morally right, Rousseau presented an optimistic view of humanity. This optimism in the human condition and the inner strength which it further implies provided American writers with a suitable subject with which to explore the concept of a tabula rasa of this new nation. If man in his primitive state is the raw material from which a morally good and just citizen might emerge, then a logical literary extension of this idea was the association of this new nation, the United States of America, with the same state.

The philosophy of Rousseau exhibits a social idealism which encourages man to actively regenerate society and renovate social institutions. Rather than accept the prevailing socio-political philosophy, Rousseau, who places man's natural freedom at the core of his political philosophy, proposes that man retreat from entrenched ideology and turn, instead, toward the creation of a social system which will foster equality among all men.

Viewing the social system as composed of artificial convention which requires individual men to assume masks and to interact in ways which are

artificial to the true human nature, Rousseau calls for a return to natural action founded on reason of mind and heart. Instinct, feeling, subjectiveness, and imagination are of paramount importance to his thinking and they are to be employed to lead enlightened men from the state of nature to the social state, which is the appropriate state. (54)

With regard to developments in education during the 19th century, Rousseauist ideas came into the American educational system in much the same way that they were introduced throughout Europe during this time: via the influence of predominating European educational reformers such as the Swiss Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi and the Germans Friedrich Fröbel and Johann Friedrich Herbart. The educational practices of Pestalozzi, whose impact was largely felt in the area of elementary education with his development of the idea of “organic” education, were brought to America through the work of William Maclure at New Harmony in Indiana and by Joseph Neef in Pennsylvania. Fröbel was responsible for the development of the concept of Kindergarten and the “self activity” or self development of the child; his student Margarethe Schurz established a German-speaking kindergarten in the United States in 1856 in Wisconsin, which inspired Elizabeth Peabody to create an English language kindergarten in Boston in 1860 (Wisconsin). The work of Herbart brought a psychological edge to the field of education, and his ideas spread through articles published in the 1880s in the *Illinois School Journal* (Somr and Hrušková) and later through meetings of the Philosophy Club and the National Herbart Society for the Scientific Study of Education (1895-1901). John Dewey criticized Herbart’s instructional methods and emphasis on the continuity of the educational process (English 105-106), but recent studies have tended to reconcile Herbart and Dewey with regard to discontinuity and rupture in education (English xix; xxiv). Particularly after 1860, then, Pestolezzi’s and Fröbel’s ideas and experiments “combined with widespread social-democratic influences on education and advances in psychologic thought to change schooling. This confluence, which was most noticeable in elementary education, resulted in the appearance of the kindergarten and in methods proceeding from the nature of the child and including content representing more of the present society.... [T]he ideas of preparing teachers to use techniques derived from the new concepts, including the greater systematization introduced by Herbart, and the necessity for teachers to learn specifically about the child would substantially augment teacher-training programs and lay the groundwork for immense institutional expansion in the first half of the 20th century” (Meyer and Lawson). Thus the impact of Rousseauist ideas on American education in the 19th century was significant.²

Rousseau’s reputation as a positive force, a harbinger of Romanticism, began to slide in the late 19th century, first as the Romantic values started to be called into doubt, then as the emergence of Socialist, Communist, and Fascist ideologies illustrated (to some) the dangers involved in such political concepts as the general will and the social contract.³ An early European example of this shift away from appreciation of Rousseau appears in Nietzsche’s critiques, which from some angles could be seen as almost expressions of vituperation toward the Rousseauist position. In America, on the other hand, extensive criticism of Rousseau and his impact on society appears at this time in the works of

Irving Babbitt, especially in his book *Rousseau and Romanticism*. By the end of World War Two and with the beginning of the Cold War, American studies on Rousseau had moved toward the problematic, particularly as regards the political sphere and Rousseauist ideas on education and the role of reason. On one hand, critics in this period found Rousseau's writings polarized or contradictory at best, and sometimes even irrelevant to the contemporary world. On the other hand, some found in Rousseau's writings foundations for political systems and beliefs about the individual that increasingly threatened Anglo-American democracy and the vision of democratic righteousness expressed in the concept of the "free world." These latter, negative readings of Rousseau were supported in the 1960s with covert though then-stylish psychoanalytical incursions into the life of the Citizen of Geneva and counteracted by the more positive readings of Rousseau offered by countercultural figures such as Arnold Kaufman (Mattson 211-212) and Huey P. Newton (Jeffries). Since then, ideological attacks on Rousseau's philosophy have continued in the critical commentaries of Jonathan Israel and (more crudely) in the manifestos of Christian conservative Michael Coffman.

An early Cold-War reading that emphasized the fundamental duality in Rousseau's writings was Leo Strauss' 1947 essay "On the Intentions of Rousseau," a study of Rousseau's *Discours sur les sciences et les arts* (first *Discours*) that saw this work as key to understanding Rousseau's philosophy. Strauss, whom J. David Hoeveler associates with Irving Babbitt (Hoeveler 182), begins his study by claiming that "The antiquarian controversy about the intention of Rousseau conceals a political controversy about the nature of democracy" (Strauss 455), and that Rousseau "considered himself the first theoretician of democracy" (455), "attack[ing] the Enlightenment as a pillar of despotism or of absolute monarchy" (457), largely because of its hostility to religion and because of the suggestion (derived from Montesquieu's *De l'esprit des lois*) that modern societies substitute commerce for virtue. This attack did not prevent Rousseau from covertly acknowledging the value of Enlightenment; it in fact led him to emphasize the distinction between "society" and the intelligentsia, and to turn his argument in the first *Discours* regarding the dangers of science into a reading of how these dangers apply to the common man. As Strauss puts it, "[i]n opposition to the Enlightenment, [Rousseau] reasserts the crucial importance of the natural inequality of men with regard to intellectual gifts" (486). Thus Strauss argues that "when Rousseau rejects science as superfluous or harmful, he speaks in the character of a common man addressing common men, and when speaking in that character, he does not exaggerate at all by rejecting science absolutely. But far from being a common man, [Rousseau] is a philosopher who merely appears in the guise of a common man: as a philosopher addressing philosophers he naturally takes the side of science" (464). Therefore the *Discours* presents two Rousseaus, Rousseau the commoner and Rousseau the philosopher. It also aims at two audiences, the audience of commoners and the audience of philosophers, and provides different messages for each. The dangers of science exist for the commoner, not for the "great minds," among whom Rousseau includes himself. As Strauss puts it, "science is permissible or salutary only in so far as it is not, as such, a social factor. Its social effect is necessarily disastrous: enlightenment paves the way for despotism.... [I]n rejecting popularized science Rousseau ... expressed directly and adequately what he seriously

thought” (467). It is for this reason, Strauss maintains, that Rousseau finds his ideal classical model in Sparta instead of in Athens (467), and perhaps this sort of understanding lies behind his support of civil religion in the *Contrat social*.

One consequence of this dualistic perspective is that it questions the viability or value of comprehensive education for the masses, a point that could be supported (though Strauss does not do so) in light of the attention to individualized education that is highlighted in Rousseau’s *Emile*. Another consequence is that Strauss’ approach realigns the standpoint many critics take on Rousseau’s frankness or sincerity. For Strauss, Rousseau’s insistence on “the obligation to speak the truth is founded exclusively on the utility of truth.... [O]ne may not only suppress or disguise truths devoid of all possible utility, but may even be positively deceitful about them by asserting their contraries, without thus committing the sin of lying” (470). “The *Discours* is so far from siding with truth as such that it attacks science precisely because it is concerned with truth as such, regardless of its utility, and hence is not, by its intention, protected against the danger of leading to useless or even harmful truths” (471). Rousseau’s emphasis on a faith based on senses and feelings and his upholding of local social values (as opposed to universal scientific or philosophical truths) is explained by this sense of duality. Indeed, “one misunderstands Rousseau’s notion of natural goodness if one does not bear in mind the fact that it refers to two different types, who stand at the opposite poles of humanity (the primitive man and the wise) and who yet belong together as natural men, as self-sufficient beings, or ‘numerical units’, in contradistinction to ... the citizen or social man, that is, the man who is bound by duties or obligations and who is only a ‘fractionary unit’” (476-477). “Society has to do everything possible to make the citizens oblivious of the very facts that are brought to the center of their attention, as the foundations of society, by political philosophy” (482). In educational terms, this pertains to Strauss’ assertion that “Modern democracy might seem to stand or fall by the claim that ‘the method of democracy’ and ‘the method of intelligence’ are the same” (455), an assertion that might be used to call into question the value of extensive intellectual emphasis in education, and that Timothy Fuller suggests might refer to positions on education advocated by John Dewey (Fuller 241, note 2).

Strauss’ reading implicates Rousseau in a sense of political duplicity that might have matched the expectations of some egregious Cold Warriors of his time in the way they would judge the enemy, but the connection is never spelled out, only implied in the suggestion that Rousseau supports a split between philosophy, science, or intelligentsia on the one hand, and the common man on the other. What is more reflective of other perspectives in this approach is the suggestion of some sort of contradictory force at work in Rousseau’s writings. Other critics also point to this sense, though not in ways that necessarily imply manipulation. Judith Shklar, for instance, studies Rousseau’s writings in their relation to the utopian dreams of Spartan society and the autonomous family found in *La Nouvelle Héloïse*. Reminding us that “Rousseau is not ‘rousseauisme’” (*Men* 216), and that the “the *Social Contract* was less a utopia than a book of warnings” (*Men* 211), Shklar suggests that the application of Rousseau’s writings to any political or social model is fraught with danger:

The combination of a psychology and a moral outlook exclusively concerned with the needs of the individual, an extreme hatred for inequality, and an intense dislike for change make it particularly useless to impose the conventional classifications of later political theory upon Rousseau. He was neither a traditionalist nor a revolutionary of any sort. So deep a hatred of inequality is a perpetual challenge to any known society. (*Men* 30)

The problem with the model lies in part in its pitting of the need for personal fulfillment (the Clarendon model) against the needs of self-abnegation in the idealized classical Spartan model. We see the conflict explored, for example, in Rousseau's concerns about happiness, a "public" good that is as deeply intimate and personal as any feeling can be. Shklar writes, "[s]ince happiness is the sole object of men's striving, the legitimate society, like any other human enterprise must be judged in terms of its ability to satisfy the most universal aspiration. Rousseau did not forget it. The sovereign people must feel a 'public happiness'. Like the general will it is a metaphor of personification. For happiness is the most individual and personal of feelings, as Rousseau realized very well. This evidently made it difficult to speak of it as something 'public', and after worrying the notion of '*le bonheur publique*' in several fragments, he used it rather sparingly in his finished political writings" (*Men* 193). Behind these difficulties, Shklar suggests, lie Rousseau's concerns with "his own inner life, the needs of his own self" (*Men* 121), and a bevy of conflicting forces that work behind the scenes of his political, literary, educational, and other writings: a hatred of inequality matched by an uneasiness with equality, and an ongoing conflict between "an urge for perfect freedom and a longing for submission" (*Men* 130). In this context, one could argue (though here Shklar does not) that *Emile* represents an exploration of educational strategies that direct the pupil toward self-sufficiency in an effort to approximate happiness by teaching the pupil to live according to his basic needs, qualities, and moral code, within realistic boundaries set by the human condition.

A position Shklar does maintain, though, is that if "[b]y nature men are free ... left to their own devices they will inevitably enslave each other" ("Rousseau's Images" 919). This example of the "bipolarities" in Rousseau's thought underlies Rousseau's constant assertion of the need for a master, be it tutor or prince, to direct human behavior, since "*amour-propre* ... reinforces the actuality of weakness, though it hides it as each person comes to think of himself only in competitive comparison with others" ("Rousseau's Images" 919). However, Rousseau knew too well that too often in society, "authority was exercised only to maintain a destructive and false order" ("Rousseau's Images" 921), creating societies that are marked by "pride and cruelty at the top, servility and dishonesty at the bottom" ("Rousseau's Images" 921). In light of these tendencies, at the individual level, Rousseau required "tutorial vigilance" ("Rousseau's Images" 923) to protect the "God-given self which forms the core of ... character. This personal self is not inherently hostile to other selves, nor does it thrive in permanent solitude" ("Rousseau's Images" 923). Because of the contrast between the requirements of the social order and the wish to free the individual from subservience to this unavoidable order, "[C]ivic education and the education of the individual have nothing in common" ("Rousseau's

Images” 924). On the one hand, in *Emile*, the master’s goal is to “fulfill [a] task of prevention. The child is to be educated *against* society and he must be protected against parents, neighbors and servants who would press their false values upon him” (“Rousseau’s Images” 930). On the other hand, “The conflict between the ideals of personal authority and of impersonal law [is] resolved in Rousseau’s mind by making law ... subordinate” since “ultimately the rule of law also depends upon a single human voice and hand to give it life” (“Rousseau’s Images” 922). Systems of national encouragement of obedience to the law through education, such as Rousseau explores in “Political Economy” (20-23), require vigilance, but even more, they require the weight of the authoritative leader who can convince the public of the virtues of law:

The great problem of politics is to make governments the guardians, rather than the enemies of law. [But] law is psychologically ineffective. It can condition only external behavior. Public opinion and mores alone can touch the heart. To be truly effective public authority must penetrate to the very heart. To do this requires more than law, it depends on continuing education... Law ultimately is what personal authority can give society for a while.... That was the way of those ancient political paragons Moses, Lycurgus, Numa and Solon. (“Rousseau’s Images” 922)

If education here “replaces not only the father, but the entire family” (929), it does so in order to ensure that the pupil become “a self-sufficient adult who lives at peace with himself” (“Rousseau’s Images” 930), removed from the forces of *amour-propre* that drive and, too often, destroy or corrupt society. Rousseau’s famous proposal of negative education comes into play here, since negative education “prevents the imposition of an artificial, socially devised and socially oriented self upon the child” (“Rousseau’s Images” 930). Beneath this freedom, or at least directing it, is the constant presence of “an educative, preventive, curative and ordering authority. Authentic authority liberates. It gives liberty to those who are incapable of creating it for themselves” (“Rousseau’s Images” 931).

As we have suggested above, Shklar’s Rousseau is confronted with conflicts internal and external that often seem to be only tenuously resolved. Patrick Riley’s Rousseau also confronts contradictions, but these contradictions concern his allegiances to the modern state and to the classical model of democracy. Riley’s interest in explaining the concept of the general will in Rousseau revolves around his insight that the general will “is an attempted (though not explicit) amalgam of two extremely important traditions of political thought, which may be called, roughly, ancient ‘cohesiveness’ and modern ‘voluntarism’” (“Possible Explanation” 86). The problem Rousseau faced in the concept of the general will, in other words, was to reconcile modern individualist and even commercialized models of society with the greater cohesiveness he perceived in ancient societies. By attempting to join an individual willingness to participate in society with an overall social good, Rousseau hoped to assure the legitimacy of power in society. But “while voluntarism took care of legitimacy, it could say nothing about the intrinsic goodness of what is willed” (“Possible Explanation” 87). In modern societies, as compared to classical societies, “imperfect socialization ... allowed private persons and

corporate interests to control other private persons, leading to extreme inequality” (“Possible Explanation” 88). The idea of the general will emerges from these conflicts: the “transformed society must be governed on the basis of common interest ... only general laws, the creation of a general will (sovereignty), can govern the common interest” (“Possible Explanation” 92). The uniting of particular wills with the general will depends upon the efforts of a “great legislator” (“Possible Explanation” 94) who obliges individuals to conform their particular wills to reason. Riley sums up his argument as follows:

1) a perfect state (that is, a perfectly socialized, united, and communal state) would have perfectly general laws (that is, laws dealing only with Rousseau’s vision of a common good); 2) but laws, especially the most general laws, must be willed by everyone subject to those laws, in order to be obligatory — and they must be made obligatory, for society is merely conventional; 3) therefore, will must take the form of general laws; 4) but will tends to the particular, and law, though the creation of will, must somehow be general; 5) moreover, for particular wills to appreciate the necessity of general laws, effect would have to become cause; 6) therefore, a great legislator, whose instruction can supply the defect of a morality of the common good — the only morality which would naturally produce general laws — is necessary; 7) but this legislator is impossibly rare, and, in addition, he cannot create laws, however general and good, for sovereignty is inalienable; 8) thus the legislator must have recourse to religion, and use it to gain the consent of individuals to the general will; 9) but now “consent” is something less than real consent, since an irrational device has been used; 10) finally, the whole system is saved for individual will by the fact that “a people always has a right to change its laws, even the best,” that legislative will, rather than law itself, is supreme, and that the entire social system can be abolished by will, for “there is not, and cannot be, any sort of fundamental law binding on the body of the people, not even the social contract.” (“Possible Explanation” 95)

Riley would later describe the legislator as a “civic educator” who brings about a transformation of natural, egoistic individuals into a citizenry that freely conjoins with the general will. The linking of politics and education means that the function of education is to transform “naturally self-loving egoists animated only by their own ‘private wills’ into *polis*-loving citizens with a civic ‘general will’” (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 573). This “radically *transformative* education” aims to make people “what they ought to be” (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 573). At the same time, this “transformative” and “denaturing” education must “produce autonomous adults who can say to their teachers (with Emile), ‘What course have I chosen! To remain what you have made me’” (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 574). The “rigorous civic education” Riley here describes Rousseau as presenting draws “natural beings out of their (equally natural) ego-centrism, bringing them to think of themselves (finally) as ‘parts of a greater whole’ — a whole less extensive, but more realisable, than a ‘Christian republic’ or a kingdom of ends” (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 579). Rousseau’s aim, for Riley, is thus to “generalise’

will — either through civic education, as in the *Social contract* or the *Considerations on the government of Poland*, or through private education, as in *Emile*” (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 582). If there is paradox in this consideration of educational strategy, Riley suggests, this is inevitable, since Rousseau’s theories work via progression through paradox:

For Rousseau there are unavoidable stages in all education, whether private or public. The child, he says in *Emile*, must first learn necessity, then utility, and finally morality, in that inescapable order. If one says ‘ought’ to an infant he simply reveals his own ignorance and folly. The notion of necessary educational time, or *becoming* what one was not, is revealed perfectly in Emile’s utterance, when he chooses ‘to remain what you have made me’. That is deliberately paradoxical — many of Rousseau’s central moral / political beliefs are cast in the form of paradoxes. However, it does show that the capacity to ‘decide’ is indeed ‘made’. It is education that ‘forces one to be free’ — by slowly ‘generalising’ the will. Similarly, Rousseau’s ‘nations’ are at first ignorant.... [A]utonomy arrives at the end of a process, and the general will is *at last* as enlightened as it was (always) right. (“Rousseau’s Philosophy” 584)

Patrick Riley thus supplies us with a summation of Rousseau’s concept of the general will, and sees this force as ultimately enlightening and formative. Roger D. Masters, in *The Political Philosophy of Rousseau*, provides us with another view in what he describes as an exegesis of Rousseau’s political thought. Quoting Bertrand de Jouvenel, Masters suggests that “[a]ll social evolution of the past two centuries has been contrary to the preferences of Jean-Jacques” (420). He contrasts the laws of science with the laws of human society that Rousseau had linked together, and argues in his concluding chapter that this linkage is what makes Rousseau’s political philosophy challenging in modern society. Masters points to Leo Strauss’ discussion of the distinction between the teleological aspects of the human science of natural rights and the non-teleological aspects of the science of nature as problematic for Rousseau’s perspectives. As he puts it, “Rousseau was fully aware ... of the gap between scientific propositions and the assumptions or prejudices governing civil society. But his principles of right ... appear impotent as a means of inhibiting the most enormous social experiments conducted in the name of scientific or pseudo-scientific theories of human nature; the most obvious of these theories — that of Karl Marx — has produced totalitarian political systems that sharply contradict Rousseau’s own preferences, but could conceivably be justified in terms of the enlightened or true self-interest of a citizen body which has absolute sovereignty” (423). Considering this angle, Rousseau’s “principles are open to a subversion,” or in other words can be used in a way that makes them appear responsible for totalitarian impulses.

A part of this tendency in Rousseau for Masters pertains to the nature and processes of education as Rousseau sees them. Masters points out that Rousseau’s treatise on education, *Emile*, is “written on at least two levels: while Rousseau describes the proper

education for the ‘natural man’, he also analyzes the nature of man” (3). A problem with this approach, according to Masters, is that it must start from a level that exists before the human exists; “Rousseau ... defines education broadly as that which provides ‘everything that we do not have at our birth and which we need when grown’” (5). Education, that is, involves a “denaturing” of the human, which perhaps prepares the individual for the public education described in *Political Economy*, by which prescribed public education becomes central to popular and legitimate governance (384). Such an education should be at the hands of authorities such as “‘famous warriors’ and ‘upright judges’ who have ‘worthily fulfilled’ official functions” (384), lest public confidence in the belief that education is “the most important business of the state” (384) be eroded. Rousseau’s system would then, in this view, be designed to create the ideal citizen, one who is in agreement with the “popularly accepted moral standards” (385) that underlie the general will.

In his criticism of Rousseau’s political position, Masters suggests that Rousseau’s political philosophies and assumptions about human development are largely irrelevant in the modern world. For example, Rousseau’s beliefs regarding the solitary nature of early humans, the state of freedom enjoyed in nature, the lateness of the evolution of the social contract, and so on, seem disproved by contemporary research into human evolution and social development. From Masters’ perspective, then, the *Discours sur les sciences et les arts* (first *Discours*) is the main work that continues to bear social relevance. As Masters puts it, “in some countries this epoch [at the time he was writing, the 1960s] has produced a despotism based on advanced technology, permitting total control and mobilization of huge populations to a degree apparently never before obtained” (440). “[A]n objective consideration of our own era confirms Rousseau’s claim that the pursuit of luxury and wealth based on scientific and technical progress coincided with grave social and moral problems” (441). Masters traces the significance of the *Discours* to the “general pattern of historical development in the mid-twentieth century”:

Rousseau reminded his readers of the conquest of wealthy empires by poorer rivals, and it requires particular obtuseness to fail to see, in the process of decolonization, the successful challenge to western democracies by underdeveloped or backward peoples with but a fraction of the economic and military power of their former colonial conquerors. Increasingly, present world affairs are being seen as a contest between the developed countries of the Northern hemisphere and the poorer peoples of the Southern hemisphere (442)

Thus, according to Masters, what Rousseau wrote regarding the general form of social organization, human development, the evolution of inequality, and so on bears little relevance in our modern world; it is only in the area of the challenge the developing world brings to the developed world, the conflict between north and south, that Rousseau’s writing has contemporary relevance. In this way, Rousseau’s *œuvre* seems entirely beside the point as regards such social issues of Masters’ time as the conflict between western societies and the Soviet bloc. More relevance might arguably be found in the evolving face-off between developed and developing countries, such as might be

expressed in the events following the Arab Spring. Even in education, Masters states, Rousseau is misguided, for he “attempted to determine the natural limits on human freedom in order that the end or good life for man, as an individual, could be defined without ambiguity” and “was therefore forced to ascertain certain natural characteristics or impulses which are not subject to modification or destruction within society” (425). In this process, Masters claims, Rousseau was forced to elevate conscience over reason. But for Masters, “As the experience of Nazi Germany graphically illustrates, Rousseau’s premise that the conscience of pity is a more fundamental human attribute than reason can — to say the least — be opened to scientific doubt” (426).

However, Masters raises a caveat in his discussion of readings of Rousseau: “all too often it is hard to know where Rousseau is being analyzed and where the commentator is introducing his own attitudes and ideas” (418). We can see this conflict in the perspectives on Rousseau introduced by Irving Babbitt, who played a crucial role in founding the conservative movement known as the New Humanism. Though this movement subsided in the 1930s, only to be reassessed in the 1980s (Hoeveler), Cold War academics such as J. L. Talmon and Lester G. Crocker provide a reading of Rousseau that demonstrates a perspective reminiscent of Babbitt’s cultural conservatism. These ideological readings perhaps offers grist to the mill of Rousseau criticism introduced by later writers such as Jonathan Israel and Michael Coffman.

Writing in the early twentieth century, Babbitt follows his own agenda by electing to place Rousseau at the core of his main argument regarding the negative side effects of what he calls “Romanticism.” In an attack on an aspect of Romanticism that he sees as causing the dissolution of reliable concepts and values, Babbitt endeavors to retrace the origin of the disintegration of classical values by looking closely at the Romantic movement as a whole. Though he acknowledges that the terms ‘Classic’ and ‘Romantic’ are hard to define, he believes it necessary to take the trouble to come up with definitions that throw light on what he singles out as a type of “[Romantic] movement that from Rousseau to Bergson has sought to discredit the analytical intellect” (1). Using a distinctly critical tone towards the writers he identifies as followers of Rousseau, Babbitt makes it clear that he is blatantly taking sides against Romanticism in support of what he considers ‘Classical’ values. He identifies Rousseau with an essentially ungrounded movement followed by “those who are with [Rousseau or Wordsworth] rather than with [Socrates]” (1). For Babbitt, this movement is ungrounded because it is based on abstract, imaginative, and metaphysical foundations, or in other words because it shows in its writings, according to Babbitt’s own pseudo-positivistic scientific perspective, unworthiness as regards its living up to the intellectual and ethical standards put forward by Socrates. Thus Babbitt focuses his attack on Romanticism, and on Rousseau in particular, because he establishes Rousseau as both the precursor to and the culprit behind the Romantic movement. Rousseau’s inclination, according to Babbitt, is towards the metaphysical and sentimental as opposed to the intellectual, and Babbitt declares that to “measure up to the Socratic standard, a definition must not be abstract and metaphysical, but experimental” (1). Paradoxically, this analysis even provides the key to an interpretation of educational practices that contrasts Babbitt’s ‘classical’ or ‘Socratic’ model of education with a Rousseauist ‘Romantic’ or ‘utilitarian’ approach, with a

decided favoring of the classical. One result is a collapse of practicality in any potential approach to education that follows Babbitt's inclination; as Joseph Aldo Barney puts it, Babbitt saw in the confrontation between these educational models "a life and death struggle between the apostles of utility and the advocates of tradition" (150) and "held that the naturalistic education espoused by Rousseau ... was undermining the traditional liberal arts education in the schools.... [Babbitt] feared, therefore, that attempts at humanitarian education would eventuate ... ultimately in a decline of the civilized world" (153).⁴

Reading Babbitt, it becomes clear that his approach to Rousseau and the so-called Romantic movement is deeply flawed, largely because it presumes to stem from a polarized analysis that favors a critical position based on science and experience. By interpreting Rousseau in a sweeping fashion, and by pretending that critical approaches that are founded on history and pseudo-scientific methods allow for accurate comprehension of texts, Babbitt reveals the lack of nuance inherent in his understanding of the mechanisms of the text and its various expressions. Indeed, one of Babbitt's criticisms is that Romanticism relies on an irrelevant adoption of an 18th century ideal that bases its views on truth and the world on "the law for things" as opposed to the "laws for man" that have come into being through the development of civilization. This perspective presumably underlies the critique of utilitarian educational approaches that by nature must address themselves to aspects of physical reality. Another criticism Babbitt makes, this time expressly of Rousseau even though it extends to the 18th century at large, is that not only Romanticism, as he defines it, but also Deism, which enables man to find harmony not in the rules of Christian dogma but in oneself and in nature, has caused a break with the Christian tradition and led to a finding of the powers of virtue in "sense," in an instinct that directs morality itself into "an aesthetic or sentimental morality" (44). Says Babbitt, "Man begins to discover harmonies instead of discords in himself and [in] outer nature. He not only sees virtue in instinct but inclines to turn virtue itself into a 'sense' or 'instinct'. And this means in practice to put emotional expansion in the place of spiritual concentration at the basis of life and morals" (44).

It is true that *Emile* does seem to reject history and the subjective laws of Man, and that it relies essentially on the needs and necessities of nature as opposed to systematic ideologies. But it is also important to remember that Rousseau's philosophy does not do away with the values of experience. It in fact advocates control of the imagination whenever imagination threatens to go astray at the expense of judgment, acknowledges history whenever it discloses the recognition of behaviors that are universally worthy of our morals as opposed to being the object of propaganda for any given regime, and above all incorporates into the educational process that has been developed for the child the use of reason, starting with the encouragement of common sense, or with the development in *Emile* of what Rousseau calls « *la raison sensitive* » before presenting to the child's intellect the many complex aspects that interfere with the use of intellectual reason. Thus when Babbitt pretends not to reject a naturalism that serves a utilitarian and scientific purpose, but only to reject that type of naturalism that reflects the unsound aspects of a Rousseauistic philosophy of life — "if I am right in my conviction as to the unsoundness of a Rousseauistic philosophy of life, it follows that the total tendency of the occident at

present is away rather than towards civilization” (x) — we can only assume that he has misunderstood Rousseau’s intent as well as Rousseau’s writings. The misunderstanding is revealed by the fact that Babbitt identifies the Romanticism associated with Rousseau with an “emotional naturalism” that leads to excesses through the adoption of unreliable and relativistic values. As Babbitt puts it, “my argument on the positive side aims to reassert the ‘law for man’, and its special discipline against the various forms of naturalistic excess” (x). ‘Naturalistic excess’ for Babbitt is tantamount to using imagination to let sentiment prevail over intellect and reason, creating an ungrounded, utopian, unrealistic world that is reflected in the unleashing of the ethically questionable Romantic genius.

We see an example of this confusion when Babbitt accuses Schiller of looking for a driving power in emotion, not in “supersensuous reality, not [in] insight,” because Schiller chose as a motto for his “Aesthetic Letters from Rousseau” the phrase « *Si c’est la raison qui fait l’homme, c’est le sentiment qui le conduit* » (43). Babbitt here demonstrates just how much he misunderstands Rousseau’s use of the words ‘sentiment’ and ‘nature’. Far from referring to relative expressions in humanity that are subject to outside stimuli, these terms signify for Rousseau sensible, evaluative measures that represent universal components of human nature, both at large and in practice. The terms also point to subjective components, but in doing so they are not just indicating superficial adoptions of an anarchistic credo that will lead 20th century man, for lack of accepting the conventions that have been an unquestionable gift of civilization, to social chaos and political absolutism. Indeed, a focus on the contrast between convention and nature sums up what Babbitt sees as much of the legacy of Rousseauism:

In permitting his expansive impulses to be disciplined by either humanism or religion man has fallen away from nature much as in the old theology he has fallen from God, and the famous ‘return to nature’ means in practice the emancipation of the ordinary or temperamental self that had been thus artificially controlled. This throwing off of the yoke of both Christian and classical discipline in the name of temperament is the essential aspect of the movement in favor of the original genius. The genius does not look to any pattern that is set above his ordinary spontaneous ego and imitate it. On the contrary, he attains to the self expression that other men, intimidated by convention, weakly forego.

In thus taking a stand for self-expression, the original genius is in a sense on firm ground — at least so far as the mere rationalist or the late and degenerate classicist is concerned. No conventions are final, no rules can set arbitrary limits to creation. Reality cannot be locked up in any set of formulae [except] abysmal, unsearchable and infinite multiplicity. (45-46)

If Babbitt recognizes that what has happened to Rousseauism in the 19th and 20th centuries is no longer absolutely a reflection of Rousseau’s philosophy, one can say that he surely uses some of Rousseau’s terminology to establish Rousseau as the very initiator

and cause of the forces that have created a series of social and political upheavals in the 19th and the 20th centuries.

One may wonder if Babbitt is victim of his own strong desire to see himself as a scientist of literature, as someone who has adopted the criteria of the author's life and his work as an absolute mode of interpretation. Yet it goes without saying that this single-minded interpretation, narrowed down to a rejection of Classicism and Christianity, and his desire to depict Rousseau's endeavor as essentially narcissistic, as reflecting a project that has led to an anarchic free-for-all in the adoption of values that infect other realms of human science via the bias of literature, paradoxically demonstrates the birth of deconstruction. In fact the position that Babbitt takes assumes the pretense that one can understand an author without acknowledging his voice, so that one feels perfectly legitimized in attaching all kinds of unforeseen interpretations to the text in the name of its syntactic and semantic distributions.⁵ But one cannot limit oneself solely to reading Rousseau in light of the idiosyncrasies of his style or his bewitching lyricism; one owes it to him to read him not only in light of his intentions as they are translated in the gesture of writing, but also in light of all his other texts, most written within a decade. An expanded reading such as this reveals how Rousseau's views do not rely on an egocentric understanding of humanity, which he would have seen as based on an understanding of society anchored in *amour-propre* rather than one based in a community founded on *amour de soi*. This latter type of community would feature a concept of individuality that requires a recognition of the interweaving of the individual and his original, pure make-up (the source of humanity) with the a priori expression of a society in which conscience relies on a universal compassion that is demonstrated via humanity's innate *amour de soi* and translated into the power of the general will. If one wishes to lend to Rousseau's philosophy an egotistic slant, then, one can only do so on behalf of a reader who interprets Rousseau's theories as duplicitous and dangerous, because this same reader is subject to an agenda and to some kind of projection.

Even though after the late 1930s Modernist, Progressivist, and other movements diminished some of the authority attributed to Babbitt's New Humanism, it is hard not to see the influence Babbitt's ideas had on the investigations of later academics. In a vein of interpretation that recalls aspects of Babbitt's approach, for instance, J. L. Talmon identifies in Rousseau's ideas part of an encapsulation of perspectives that led to the birth of democratic totalitarianism.⁶ According to Talmon, it is no longer a question of the relativistic interpretation of values that Babbitt saw as the cause of the collapse of good Classical teachings in mankind, but in fact a question of the pretentious absolutism of a bunch of so-called doctrinarian thinkers, "prophets of liberty and the rights of man" (4), who saw "the idea of man as an abstraction" and evaluated the condition of humanity no longer in relation to an established order, but independently from "the historic groups to which [persons] belong[ed]," relying on ideologies that were susceptible of becoming "a powerful vehicle of totalitarianism" (4). Talmon sees the most important change in the 18th century as one involving a "peculiar state of mind" that considered the human legacy as unnatural and unworthy: "Men were gripped by the idea that the conditions, a product of faith, time and custom, in which they and their forefathers had been living, were unnatural and had all to be replaced by deliberately planned uniform patterns, which

would be natural and rational” (3). According to Talmon, this new secular religion that usurped the rights of the Church promoted “social morality,” since it was now incumbent upon the State to supply or replace the religious ethics that used to exist. Liberty was hence to be achieved “only in the pursuit of a collective purpose” (4) that was rooted in social utility rather than in tradition, and that above all was guided by reason (3). These new thinkers, armed with the conviction that there was no other truth than an “exclusive truth in politics” (1),

refused to envisage the conflict between liberty and virtue as inevitable. On the contrary, the inevitable equation of liberty with virtue and reason was the most cherished article of their faith. When the 18th century secular religion came face to face with this conflict, the result was the great schism. Liberal democracy flinched from the spectre of force, and fell back upon the trial-and-error philosophy. Totalitarian Messianism hardened into an exclusive doctrine presented by a vanguard of the enlightened who justified themselves in the use of coercion against those who refused to be free and virtuous. (5)

Having defined the partisans of “the totalitarian school” as a bunch of doctrinarians who cherished what they perceived as an exclusive truth in politics because their ideology postulated “a preordained, harmonious and perfect scheme of things, to which men [were] irresistibly driven and at which they [we]re bound to arrive” (2), and in addition having defined these thinkers as despotic re-enforcers of a dubious new secular ethic that served as justification of the right to coerce in the name of freedom and virtue, Talmon points to what he interprets as the shifting of the original credo from a mainly ethical stance into “a social and economic doctrine” that nevertheless still is “based on ethical premises,” and that is thereby added to the overall picture of a makeshift, opportunistic movement rather than to a grounded, sensible and humanitarian one:

[B]efore the eighteenth century had come to an end, the inner logic of political Messianism, precipitated by the Revolutionary upheaval, its hopes, its lessons and its disappointments, converted the secular religion of the eighteenth century from a mainly ethical into a social and economic doctrine, based on ethical premises. The postulate of salvation, implied in the idea of the natural order, came to signify to the masses stirred by the Revolution a message of social salvation before all. And so the objective ideal of social harmony gave place to the yearnings and strivings of a class; the principle of virtuous liberty to the passion for security. The possessing classes, surprised and frightened by the social dynamism of the idea of the natural order, hastened to shake off the philosophy which they had earlier so eagerly embraced as a weapon in their struggle against feudal privilege. The Fourth Estate seized it from their hands, and filled it with new meaning. And so the ideology of the rising bourgeoisie was transformed into that of the proletariat. (5-6)

If, in this formulation of the ideals perpetuated in the eighteenth century, one can recognize themes that are prevalent in Rousseau's philosophy, such as notions of nature, freedom, and virtue, it is difficult nonetheless for a careful and sensible reader to point to them as the essential ingredients that brought into being a type of democracy that becomes a perfect model for totalitarianism. Yet Talmon ends his introduction by pointing out that "Modern totalitarian democracy is a dictatorship resting on popular enthusiasm ... [i]n so far as it is the outcome ... of the synthesis between the eighteenth-century idea of the natural order and the Rousseauist idea of popular fulfillment and self expression" (6). Talmon then continues by denouncing the misuse of reason as well as the notion of the general will as it is presented in Rousseau's ideology, saying that "By means of this synthesis rationalism was made into a passionate faith. Rousseau's 'general will', an ambiguous concept, sometimes conceived as valid a priori, sometimes as immanent in the will of man, exclusive and implying unanimity, became the driving force of totalitarian democracy, and the source of all its contradictions and antinomies" (6).

Any nuanced reader of Rousseau will have to question the accuracy of Talmon's understanding of Rousseau's general will, even if that reader might also agree that in Rousseau's philosophy, the general will can seem like a shifting and ambiguous concept. Perhaps what may help the reader see the problem with Talmon's perspective is Talmon's own eagerness to split Rousseau's concepts into oppositional categories, resulting in situations where the adoption of a principle automatically excludes the foundations on which it may have been established. When, for example, in his chapter on totalitarian democracy and Rousseau, Talmon writes about the implications involved in embracing the general will, he sees this embracing as connected to a dangerous tendency to persuade the individual that he or she is *not* being coerced into following the demands of an external standard that is being reinforced by an external authority that supposedly is answering to "man's inner voice," thus encouraging the person to submit and comply to a state of freedom that can only be achieved through discipline. Says Talmon, "even if constrained to obey the external standard, man cannot complain of being coerced, for in fact he is merely made to obey his own true self. He is thus free; indeed freer than before. For freedom is the triumph of the spirit over natural, elemental instinct. It is the acceptance of moral obligation and the disciplining of irrational and selfish urges by reason and duty" (40). In this interpretation "the whole aim of political life is to educate and prepare men to will the general will without any sense of constraint" (42), and the goal of the Legislator is "the re-education of the ... nation to will the general will" (49).

In this reading, for Talmon, the general will is something that Rousseau "conjures up" by "fiat" (19). But conversely to what Talmon seems to suggest by this characterization, the general will is not an opportunistically fuzzy concept, but rather becomes a fluid and clear expression of the best of humanity, both in its natural and in its socialized expressions. The general will in fact allows the community *and* the individual to question the purity of any and all intentions and of any disinterestedness in light of an attempt to achieve inner and outer harmony. The external standards it establishes are not arbitrary, but in fact reflect internal standards associated with the compulsions of conscience. Far from involving moralistic prescription, then, the general will is the

expression of the collective conscience at work. Also, far from acting as a Machiavellian stratagem devised to impose and perpetuate socialized moral constructs, the general will, through its flexibility, accommodates accurate uses of intuition and sensible knowledge that serve both the individual and the community. Thus freedom is not achieved through a split between instinct and spirit; it is achieved through the creation of an inner harmony that becomes the general will or the collective conscience.

According to Rousseau, selfish urges do not need to be disciplined by reason and duty if one undergoes an educational process similar to Emile's, including an embracing of negative education and a cultivation of faculties that enable one to function properly. Instinct and intuition will be combined in a well-directed flow of energy, thus letting passions flow adequately in a way that does not go against one's own well-being. In no way is the individual citizen/subject forced into obligation and acceptance, having his or her personality molded according to external political norms that have been designed to make it fit in and initiate the person into an artificial freedom. The general will is not based on notions of conformity, nor is it an external, egotistic force in relation to the individual. It enables the individual and the community to perform acts of conscience because it never goes against anyone's compassionate natural or social make up, but instead reflects the workings of the uncorrupted individual's *amour de soi*.⁷

Talmon tells us that the general will "has an objective existence of its own, whether perceived or not ... [and that it] has nevertheless to be discovered by the human mind" (41). What seems to lead Talmon to compartmentalize Rousseau's ideas here is a profound misinterpretation of Rousseau's understanding of reason. For Talmon, reason is a solely mental construct. But Rousseau, continuing in the tradition of Descartes, for whom reason stems from a capacity for common sense that is based in the expression of instinct, sees reason and reasoning not only as the articulation of a complex faculty that demands the use of a well-trained mind, but also as the manifestation of a basic faculty that starts its work before any other mental faculty develops. Before reaching maturity, the child relies mostly on what Rousseau calls « *la raison sensitive* », a basic faculty linked to the need for survival. The somewhat elusive concept of the general will is not connected for Rousseau to some externalized social abstraction like the one Talmon suggests; it exists within us as a manifestation of a potential derived from basic instinctual reasonableness. Above all, it does not have an existence of its own, outside of human reality, because it is a metaphorical concept that acknowledges a natural form of conscience that does not issue from the application of social morals, but from individuals themselves, before any exposure to ethics. It certainly does not exist solely as a mental construct; rather, it resides in the physical, anatomical, and spiritual weave of the natural man, as well as in the social man who is harmoniously tuned to nature.

Thus conversely to Talmon's idea that the human mind needs to be acquainted to the general will, the human mind of "the natural man made to inhabit the city," such as Emile is, is fully engaged with the dynamic interplay of the instinctual and the mental, since from an early age this mind has been integrated with human reasoning processes via the universal language of the body that resides at all levels of any being, from bodily microcellular reactions to the tuning of a discerning mind via the intelligence of the heart.

To see this process at work, one need only recall the early, non-verbal teaching of the infant via the stimulation of feelings, the use of simple images, and the introduction of simple thoughts (and later, as the child grows, more complex thoughts) that enable the individual, thanks to a sound and grounded intellect, to function in harmony with both himself and his surroundings. Rousseau's philosophy does not rely on changing the core of human nature, but on directing the passions in such way that the integrity of the individual's natural energy is protected and does not deviate. If the mind has learned to use its faculties properly, it is in tune with its own intuition and instinct. Thus, when Talmon asserts that an implication of Rousseau's *Social Contract* is that "[i]ndividualism will have to give place to collectivism, egoism to virtue, which is the conformity of the personal to the general will" (42), one cannot help but note that this interpretation confuses the notion of individualism, "an ideology that privileges and celebrates individuals over the group," with that of individuality, or "the recognition that individuals are different from one another" (Loo).⁸ To be sure, Rousseau's philosophy does ask that one not act selfishly, but this request has nothing to do with the imposition of rules, or with discipline, or with the obliteration of the individual's existence. Rather, it involves the reiteration of the recognition of natural compassion and pity that is born out of *amour de soi*.

The understanding that Talmon has of Rousseau's individual relies exclusively on a definition of man that is associated with *amour-propre* and not with *amour de soi*. Above all, Talmon seems to mix up the concepts of the national will and the political will with the general will, turning the latter into a means for finding an efficient way to move masses. Yet Rousseau's establishment of a social compact is not geared toward finding hypocritical ways to manipulate the mass so it will concur with the agenda of the state, but rather toward preserving the integrity of the individual through an agreement that respects each individual's wholeness while enabling the wholeness of the newly established community and state to exist in accordance with primordial principles of human compassion. Far from being a coercive mechanism that forces unanimity, it ensures the development of a process for generating and remembering wholeness and cohesion. In addition, the general will is not designed to reinforce a political agenda and a system that imposes preordained rules that apply in society without ever being questioned. Rather than considering the political plane as the only plane of existence, it brings together the natural, the instinctual, the intuitive, the individual, and the social as well as the universal planes.

By not seeing in Rousseau's definition of reason the crucial role played by instinct and common sense, Talmon falls into the same error as Babbitt did when he chooses to describe Rousseau's philosophy as based exclusively on instinct and sentiment, rather than seeing it as a philosophy that comprehensively co-ordinates the senses and the intelligence of the mind as well as the intelligence of the heart — in short, as a philosophy that combines the multidimensional aspects of the person that contribute to the intelligent use of faculties when body, mind, and heart are united. When Talmon contrasts the "liberal type of democracy" with the "totalitarian democratic school" by pointing out that totalitarian democracy "is based upon the assumption of the sole and exclusive truth in politics," while "the liberal approach assumes politics to be a matter of

trial and error” (1), one must wonder how he can present Rousseau as the precursor of such political ideologies. For one may ask if a structure with checks and balances like those found in the model of the citizen/subject in the *Social Contract*, reflecting as they do the active involvement of all that are included in the compact as well as offering a common, comprehensive, and universal understanding of what pertains to the “moral” core of humanness and humanity, precludes spontaneity and encourages doctrinal ideologies.

Looking at Lester G. Crocker’s analysis of Rousseau, written in the late 1960s and early 1970s, one encounters again a similar type of distortion in the interpretation of Rousseau’s system. Once more, Rousseau’s terminology comes under attack, as do his motivations in writing books such as *Emile* and *The Social Contract* — books that are meant to offer solutions to mankind. Instead of trying to read Rousseau contextually, which would imply attention to the autobiographical, historical, philosophical, and spiritual forces impacting his work, Crocker’s approach involves a desire to explain Rousseau’s philosophy as reflecting a hidden agenda, or better yet as exemplifying the work of a hypocrite who changes his views whenever it suits his argument. Hence, for instance, when he is reporting on Rousseau’s demonstrations in the passage known as the *Profession de foi* from *Emile*, Crocker accuses Rousseau of conveniently, under the guise of his semi-fictional character the Vicaire Savoyard, leaving reason aside in favor of the inner light when wanting to know what is true. In Crocker’s interpretation, Rousseau tries to mask the inconsistencies in his thoughts as well as his deceptive ideas by simply shifting perspectives and conveniently when need be denigrating reason, even when doing so apparently contradicts his previous acknowledgements of reason’s importance and supremacy. In this way Crocker sums up the second conclusion drawn by the Abbé during his spiritual quest as being aimed at consulting the inner light instead of at “philosophers [who] in their pride lead us only into the kingdom of confusion” (2:146). According to Crocker, Rousseau replaces Descartes’ reason with the word “heart,” the heart here representing the sensible means of reaching clarity in one’s convictions. Denouncing what he calls Rousseau’s dubious method, Crocker underlines what he sees as Rousseau’s lack of integrity and honesty

So much for the method. Only it is not really his method. In reality, Rousseau is a reasoner and a rationalist. He will reason as hard as he can. He is also a dogmatist. Knowing in advance what he wants to prove, he will abandon reason, mock and vilify it when it abandons him, and turn in triumph to the “inner light.” The “inner light” is infallible because it is an immediate intuition, preverbal in form, unfiltered by reason. He sees no contradiction in his attitude: reason, “properly” used, within its “proper” sphere, is man’s attribute. But he also decries reason, because he is hostile to its effects as men have used it in civilization. (2:146)

Crocker’s perception of Rousseau’s opportunistic use of reason here must seem completely inaccurate to anyone who has read Rousseau closely, and above all to anyone who has followed Rousseau’s multiple explanations of what the act of reasoning entails. As Rousseau points out, reason is an extremely complex faculty. To operate efficiently

and appropriately, reason requires the use not only of numerous mental faculties, but also of other physical and instinctive faculties. According to Rousseau, then, reason is not solely a mental faculty. In addition, it is not what exclusively constitutes human understanding. Seen in this light, it is certainly not the faculty of reasoning or reason in itself that Rousseau abandons, nor reason that has negative effects; rather, it is what results when men do not know how to use reason properly and comprehensively. Thus, Rousseau's statements are not brought up randomly whenever convenient; rather, they point out, as far as the use of reason is concerned, the limits of this faculty when it does not rely on other judicious faculties and detached motivations, since reasoning itself cannot merely be a simple mental exercise designed to justify our ends, especially when only superficial interests are involved. In fact, the unity of Rousseau's system and the role played by reason within it can only be understood if one recognizes the part played by conscience at the individual, instinctual, mental, spiritual, and social levels. Only then do such concepts as reason, or what Rousseau means when he deals with the notions of freedom and obedience, make sense. A more modern way of explaining where Rousseau is coming from would involve equating the notion of *amour-propre* to the ego and *amour de soi* to the self as detached entity. One wonders if Rousseau tends to be consistently misunderstood by critics such as Talmon and Babbitt because of the confusion that words such as 'reason', 'instinct', 'sentiment', 'feeling', 'opinion', 'individuality', and 'freedom' generate, or because of the meanings that these and other words convey to them. In addition, one might wonder if such critics do not project their own thoughts regarding morality onto Rousseau, due in part to their inability to understand what Rousseau really means by conscience and how it can manifest itself in a political body. As mentioned previously, Rousseau's system, as it is presented in his writings, is not meant to be seen as a series of isolated fragments that enable the critic randomly to extract statements out of context so as to project one-dimensional interpretations that are more reflective of the critic's agenda than of Rousseau's actual intentions. The now-clichéd sentence that if man does not want to be free he will be forced to be free is certainly one of the most typically misunderstood passages in the *Social Contract*, as is what Rousseau meant by the general will, which is often interpreted as representing something similar to Orwell's Big Brother.

Looking at the critics this paper has presented so far, it is incumbent to try to explain why, from the late 19th century to the contemporary period, so many Anglo-American readers of Rousseau have misunderstood his philosophy and made blatant, irrational accusations regarding his writings, especially in light of the compassionate message Rousseau was trying to put across. One might also try to explain what role historical events such as the Russian Revolution, World War Two, and the Cold War played in developing these unfounded views of Rousseau's system, as for instance in the claims concerning the totalitarian intentions that are associated with it. After all, as Dame points out, in the early history of the United States, readings of Rousseau largely remained in tune with Rousseau's intentions, including a "[call] for a return to natural action founded on reason of mind and heart" with "[i]n instinct, feeling, subjectiveness, and imagination [being] of paramount importance [and] employed to lead enlightened men from the state of nature to the social state, which is the appropriate state" (54). Perhaps Shklar's and Masters' readings of Rousseau can help explain what in Rousseau's writings triggers

fanaticism on behalf of conservative American critics, a fanaticism that can be traced to Babbitt's writings of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Neither Shklar nor Masters are invested in pointing the finger at Rousseau's system. They seem instead to want to explain or even dismiss assertions about Rousseau's importance with regard to any actual political or other manifestations from World War One to today. At question is whether Rousseau is actually a political philosopher, not to mention a politician. In fact, for Masters, Rousseau's first *Discours* is the only work that bears political relevance to modern life: "an objective consideration of our own era confirms Rousseau's claim [in the *Discours*] that the pursuit of luxury and wealth based on scientific and technical progress coincided with grave social and moral problems" (441).

On the other hand, Shklar's perspective can be seen as hinting at why hostile 20th and 21st century critics offer such compulsive misunderstandings of Rousseau; their interpretations derive from Rousseau's efforts to reconcile his longing for a society that provides opportunities for personal fulfillment with the need for self-abnegation he found in classical social models. In light of this effort Rousseau's prescriptive statements about society should not be taken literally. The concepts readers project onto his works stem from a profound misunderstanding of Rousseau's intentions, which Shklar describes as combining an endeavor to find a model that fulfills a most universal aspiration, i. e., happiness, with metaphoric personifications (the sovereign people and the general will) that aim at fostering a public model of this happiness. Reminding us that "Rousseau is not 'rousseauisme'" (216), and that the "the *Social Contract* was less a utopia than a book of warnings" (211), Shklar claims that Rousseau "was neither a traditionalist nor a revolutionary of any sort" and that his "deep ... hatred of inequality is a perpetual challenge to any known society" (30).

Riley's interpretation of Rousseau supports Masters' and Shklar's claims that Rousseau's models could represent a viable political system only with extreme difficulty. The conflict lies in Rousseau's wish to combine ancient cohesiveness and modern voluntarism. As Riley puts it, "The problem Rousseau faced in the concept of the general will ... was to reconcile modern individualist and even commercialized models of society with the greater cohesiveness he perceived in ancient societies" (86). Rousseau uses the term 'general will' to encapsulate these two notions, bringing together past and present, the community and individual, and so forth in an abstraction.

When Shklar, Masters and Riley look at Rousseau, they attempt to understand the tensions in the text that may lead to misunderstanding. They recognize the quality of Rousseau's gesture and do not try to read him literally, but rather to see what he tried to achieve. Things change when we read Rousseau from the perspectives of Babbitt, Strauss, Talmon, and Crocker. The problem these critics face is that they offer interpretations that generate ideological perspectives. Starting with Babbitt, we see an understanding of a type of Romanticism that is based on the abstract, the imaginative, the emotional, and the metaphysical, as well as on the sentimental and egocentric. Babbitt believes that this type of Romanticism aims to get rid of classical values — an interesting perspective, given Rousseau's own tendency to support his political and educational visions with direct reference to classical society, though as Riley points out, Rousseau

leans more toward Sparta than toward Athens. Babbitt's misunderstanding lies in his belief that Rousseau discredits the analytical intellect. Talmon falls into a similar error when he describes Rousseau's philosophy as based on instinct and sentiment, without the multidimensional aspect that contributes to the intelligent use of human faculties when body, mind, and heart unite. For Talmon the 18th century rebels replaced traditional values with 'natural' and rational ones, making secular religion the promoter of social morality and placing virtue and freedom in the hands of the state, not the church. Rousseau's philosophy, in Talmon's view, contributed to this movement by interjecting ideas of popular fulfillment and self expression based on instinct and sentiment, as opposed to components such as the mind and heart that can contribute to the intelligent use of faculties.

Reason itself becomes a major theme for Crocker. Strauss and Crocker both present Rousseau as a Sophist, but Crocker is more judgmental in his reading of Rousseau than Strauss is. Both Crocker and Strauss read Rousseau narrowly, in a positivistic manner (i.e., by trying to understand the text through the life of the man and by analyzing the character of the man through the perceptions reflected by the work). This approach leads them both to suggest that Rousseau is a hypocrite and to find his arguments involving manipulation and lies designed to serve his own ends. One result is that their collective analyses become almost personal. Above all, Crocker shows how completely oblivious he is of Rousseau's intentions, which involve trying to convey in his often metaphoric writing his visionary experience at Vincennes and his desire to foster ways to achieve the unity of man (see Rousseau, "To M. de Malesherbes"). None of Rousseau's writings are meant to be dogmatic, despite what Crocker so adamantly suggests, perhaps forgetting that Rousseau was self-taught and so expressed himself in uncharacteristic ways. Actually, Rousseau's writings attempt to capture a moment and transpose the revelation it involved into social, political, educational, and fictional visions. The great flaw of these conservative interpreters — Babbitt, Talmon, and Crocker — is that they read Rousseau out of context, either deliberately or unconsciously, seeing him as a manipulative, hypocritical sophist who will not hesitate to contradict himself in the name of being right. To the contrary, if Rousseau uses paradox, it is more with the intention of clarifying his vision, which he himself suggests was overwhelming, and which he acknowledges has been imperfectly relayed. As a result of their approach in reading Rousseau, then, critics such as Crocker and Strauss miss much. They do not understand Rousseau's gesture and read him literally, without nuance. This tendency reaches its extreme in the vituperation Crocker shows toward Rousseau when the former characterizes "the natural man made to inhabit the city," Emile:

Perhaps we get a more accurate view of what Emile really is, in his independence from "opinion," when we learn that he will not accept an insult or a slap, with its stain of dishonor; but neither will he, in such a situation, endanger his life to remedy what the civil law is unable to avenge. Law being insufficient, he recovers his natural independence. He will simply murder the offender in some way, perhaps by shooting him in the back. (2:144)

The extremity of the characterization here suggests that Rousseau might function for some as what Carl Jung would call a constellating factor. Though Strauss, Talmon, and Crocker lived through the Second World War and under the shadow of the Cold War, we can still see this tendency toward constellation emerging in recent presentations of Rousseauist thought, just as one can say that the “constellated” concept of the Reaganist “evil empire” has re-emerged in symbolic post-Soviet manifestations such as Islamophobia, or in the reversal of this perception in the countervailing, euphoric post-Soviet vision of the “New World Order” proclaimed by the first President Bush in the early 1990s, or in the echo of evil that streams through the plague of invective that now polarizes American politics. The ghost of history remains in the American critical psyche, and plays its role in shaping sociopolitical perspectives and the readings fueled by them much as it did in the century before. In this light we see the negative Cold War readings of Strauss, Talmon and Crocker continued in the work of two contemporary commentators, Jonathan Israel and Michael Coffman.

Jonathan Israel’s overall project is to champion what he calls the “Radical Enlightenment,” a “system of ideas that [has] shaped the Western World’s most basic social and cultural values in the post-Christian age” (*Revolution* xi). He asserts that “Radical Enlightenment argues for overthrow of current systems, the basis of morality in reason, international consensus on progress, and equality.” This intellectual movement, spawned in the 17th and 18th centuries, supports belief in fundamental human equality, stresses the importance of democracy, upholds rights of individual liberty, and argues for freedom of speech and thought. Radical Enlightenment differs from the “mainstream thinking” (*Revolution* xii) of the past, and is challenged by postmodernism, which has “deemed all traditions and sets of values more or less equally valid” (*Revolution* xiii) and so dismissed “universal ... higher values self-evident in reason and equity” (*Revolution* xiii). Israel distinguishes the Radical and Moderate Enlightenment from such “Anti-Enlightenment” figures as Rousseau.

In his systematic polarizing of perspectives, Israel connects Rousseau to authoritarianism in a way that ignores Rousseau’s support of equality. Rousseau is excluded from the Radical Enlightenment for several reasons, many of which demonstrate Israel’s ignorance of Rousseau’s positions on freedom, morality, and reason, and show how inaccurate, limited, and decontextualized his understanding of Rousseau is. Following are some of the reasons for Rousseau’s exclusion:

1. The Radical Enlightenment saw its political agenda as potentially international, arguing for “universal revolution driven by the active agent of *la philosophie*” (*Revolution* 57), and argued that human rights and equality are the same for everyone, so the revolution should be exported, while Rousseau argued against internationalism and felt that different societies would require different governmental institutions.
2. The Radical Enlightenment found the basis for morality in human reason, while Rousseau argued for its foundation in the “voice of nature.”

3. The Radical Enlightenment argued for freedom of thought and expression, while Rousseau favored censorship (“forcing people to be free”) (*Revolution* 63).
4. The Radical Enlightenment insisted on the social nature of its enterprise, while Rousseau leant increasingly towards isolation and introversion. (D’Holbach felt that the misorganization of society, which Radical Enlightenment meant to fix, was responsible for Rousseau’s contention that “life in society is ‘contrary to the nature of man’” [*Revolution* 57] and should be renounced.)
5. “Radical Enlightenment ... is partly defined by an emphatic, anti-Rousseauist preference for representative democracy” (*Revolution* 64).

Regarding these, we can agree that Rousseau certainly did not believe in “universal revolution,” which could be equated with the “New World Order” proclaimed by the first President Bush around the time of the first Gulf War. A glance at the differences between Rousseau’s recommendations for the governments of Poland and Corsica demonstrates Rousseau’s belief that different societies require different forms of government, as opposed to a “one size fits all” type of model that may underlie some of the difficulties involved in the West’s attempts to export the values (and exploitations) of capitalist society. Regarding reason, Israel’s clichéd reference to the “voice of nature” demonstrates a total lack of understanding that is perhaps even more severe than the oversimplifications of Babbitt and others. Similar problems appear with concerns about censorship. While one can detect passages suggestive of censorship in the work of Rousseau, it is only addressed directly in chapters 6-7, Book IV, of the *Social Contract*. For Rousseau, censorship is a worst-case scenario because it can only be present when it is already too late. That is to say, censorship exists only when the essential morality of the human being has been compromised by opinion, and thus when the role of negative education, as it is described in *Emile*, has failed. With regard to isolation, though Rousseau did move away from his peers, this more reflects on personality than on philosophy. And finally, as concerns representative government, see again Rousseau’s beliefs about different types of government for different societies. In short, Israel’s reading of Rousseau is filled with clichés and oversimplifications, perhaps because Israel reads Rousseau through other critics, perpetuating prejudices and distortions that lead him to miss the systematic unity in Rousseau’s thought. As an example, he concludes *Radical Enlightenment* with comments on Rousseau’s “Janus-headed mixing of elements from both the radical and mainstream Enlightenment,” proclaiming that Rousseau put “stress on the existence of a Creator and First Mover, on two substances [vs. the monadology of Israel’s champion, Spinoza], on the immortality of the soul, and the absolute quality of ‘good’ and ‘evil’ in ethics” (*Radical* 720). While some of these assertions might be supported by statements Rousseau made, the claim that Rousseau believes in an “absolute quality of ‘good’ and ‘evil’ in ethics” is blatantly false — *Emile*, for example, is *amoral* until he learns morality. Rousseau’s system is not based on a prescriptive ethics founded on absolute good and evil but rather on a natural and individual predisposition that if well channeled will inevitably construct a sensible morality, as happens for example in the case of *Emile*.

Israel's massive output has been met with an impressive range of skepticism. As Johnson Kent Wright puts it, Israel's writings have engendered “a series of in-depth critiques, from leading practitioners of every stripe,” who reach a “strikingly unanimous verdict” that the work is an “academic juggernaut, careening destructively through the discipline, in the service of a false idol ... and an unsustainable principle — the idea of an umbilical connection between metaphysical monism and political radicalism.” But if Israel's perspective is problematic, and his reading of Rousseau an amalgam of clichés, it is nothing compared with the crude ignorance displayed in the approach Michael Coffman offers in his manifesto *Rescuing a Broken America*. Coffman divides American social values into two categories that he identifies with the philosophies of John Locke and of Jean-Jacques Rousseau respectively. The Lockean model, Coffman claims, upholds the individual as the basis for any founding principle of rights and values, and so represents all “good” values of freedom and justice that underlie “true” American values as represented in the United States Constitution. The Rousseauist model, on the other hand, upholds the group or the state as determining rights and values, and so represents a movement toward evil, fascistic, and communistic values that Coffman identifies with the policies of Barack Obama. In Coffman's lexicon, “Rousseau” becomes an adjective that replaces words such as evil, lazy, dictatorial, bureaucratic, and so on, as is shown in such phrases as “Rousseau progressive liberals have a very warped view of human nature; they refuse to accept responsibility” (30) or the chapter title “The High Cost of Rousseau Socialism” (57). As regards education, Coffman argues that as a result of the “shifting [of] the form of government from that based on the John Locke model to one based in the writings of Jean Jacques Rousseau” (95), public education in America “has been totally corrupted” into “a system of mind control based on the psycho manipulation principles of Burrhus Frederic Skinner, Benjamin Bloom, and Alfred C. Kinsey” (96). The result of such an alteration is spelled out bleakly at the end of Coffman's discussion of education:

Once a revisionist curriculum indoctrinates a full generation, its propaganda becomes truth. The general population will believe that socialism and world citizenship is the only truth, and will resist all efforts to expose how they have been dumbed down. It is happening before our eyes. (104)

Anti-freedom, communistic, fascistic, evil — such are the words, images, and ideas that one finds associated with Rousseau. One might ask if these projections onto the ideas Rousseau presents are signs of isolationism and compartmentalization, Manichean perceptions of evil and duplicity, blatant representations of hypocrisy and deceit that actually only express some of the undercurrents of American society, and are unfortunately passed on in the American educational system. Such are the interpretations of Rousseau's philosophy. One can ask why Rousseau has become such a polarizing figure in Anglo-American circles, why his philosophy — or rather, attacks on his philosophy — became important in the New Humanism or underscored the orchestration of the New World Order proposed in the image of Radical Enlightenment, or even echo today across the Radical Right. An answer might lie in the tradition of Anglo-American philosophical education, which can be characterized by its *lack* of study of philosophy, bolstered by undercurrents of utilitarianism, empiricism, and pragmatism that cannot

encompass the philosophical background of someone like Rousseau, and the avowedly self-taught traditions of classical philosophy and Cartesian rationalism that he brings to his work. It might also be pertinent to consider the dismissive attitude toward foreign languages and the meanings and cultures they represent in light of this tendency to diminish the philosophical.

However we approach the phenomenon of Rousseau's denigration, what is clear is that Rousseau is a polarizing figure, an expression of contradiction and of complexity that allows critics of all stripes to see in him both what he means to say and all too often what they project. If Rousseau is a constellating figure in the Jungian sense, perhaps what the critics see in Rousseau is only a representation of themselves, or of the ideological perspectives they represent. If ideology is revealed by the contradictions it avoids, and if projection in psychological terms is the mechanism by which the analysand avoids seeing the neurotic forces driving these projections, what can we say about the characterizations of Rousseau's philosophy that underlay the long ascension of America onto the world stage from the late 19th to the 21st centuries — the period when industrialization, destruction of nature, increasingly totalitarian states, both dictatorial and democratic, and crushing social organization have come to the fore — when the statement that “man is born free, but everywhere he is in chains” has in some ways become truer than ever?

Perhaps the effort is to kill the messenger, rather than hear the actual message, in which the disunities of individual and social freedoms might be addressed, or in which the possibilities of a new freedom lie buried in an unrealizable novel on the education of a child in which the child gets taught in such a way that his mind remains unclouded by ideology, operates mostly on common sense, and enjoys a harmonious use of mental faculties, allowing him to be able to think outside the box in an open fashion at all times. Either way, what you see is what you get — or what you are. These readings or misreadings of Rousseau may then tell us as much about our own society as they do about the citizen of Geneva.

Notes

¹ For an assessment of Rousseau's impact more particularly on American life in the 18th century, see Spurlin.

² For a perhaps oversimplified view of Rousseau's impact on American education, particularly at the primary levels and regarding the shift away from Puritanical educational practices toward the introduction of Kindergarten, see Cunningham.

³ Frank Thakur Das maintains that "the period roughly speaking between 1889 and 1930 ... found the critics, mostly academics, pre-occupied in examining the elusive, metaphysical, concept of the General Will," but that "in the background of [the] rise and fall of Fascism in Europe [the] main concern was to probe into the overall political disposition of Rousseau's thought in terms of two rather loosely defined categories Liberal or Totalitarian, either variant of this critical pre-occupation which held the attention of Rousseauite scholarship for more than a decade was like-wise in terms of two, somewhat vague, yet suggestive categories, i. e. Individualism and Collectivism" (552-553).

It should also be noted here that readings of Rousseau often approach the texts in isolation, or emphasize certain features at the expense of others. It is important to remember that Rousseau generated most of his works within a decade, and that the works are supposed to complement each other. Ideally they are not to be read exclusively, but judged in light of his whole *œuvre*. Nor are they to be seen as evidence of a pre-Romantic, Enlightenment, or other tendency, but must be read from multiple perspectives at once. *Julie, ou la nouvelle Héloïse*, for instance, is well known for its exploration of political and social views, and so goes well beyond being a simple love story. Rousseau himself explains his entire *œuvre* in relation to a moment of enlightenment he experienced when traveling to Vincennes, and locates the central tenets of his philosophy in his two *Discours* and in *Emile*.

⁴ Other critics who support Babbitt's views on education in contrast to perspectives traced to Rousseau include Robert C. Koons, for whom Rousseau's "admitted ... inveterate laziness" translates (via Harvard's Charles William Eliot) into the "elective system" of the modern university, "in which the student is 'compelled to be free' by being denied the opportunity to undertake a coherent and well-ordered course of study" (Koons 203), and Glenn A. Davis, who suggests that Babbitt saw Rousseau's "understanding of the imagination" as underlying "the deepest roots of educational decay," since in the Rousseauist model, "Education ... did not mean training for ethical character or virtue, but rather it meant 'letting go' of all externally imposed standards" while also "limiting instruction to the utilitarian needs of its constituents" (Davis 53-54).

⁵ Lester G. Crocker illustrates this tendency when he tells us, "[a] major fallacy [Babbitt commits] is to regard Rousseau as an anarchist, whereas, quite to the contrary, [Rousseau]

is an authoritarian and puts the highest price on discipline and order” (“Professor Babbitt” 272). This interpretation equally reveals Crocker’s and Babbitt’s misreading of Rousseau.

⁶ According to Arie Dubnov, Talmon describes “the French Enlightenment thinkers, headed by Jean-Jacques Rousseau, as radicals who not only provided the philosophical justification for Jacobin terror but were in fact also forerunners of Bolshevism and Stalinism. Talmon considered Rousseau, more than anyone else, an anti-liberal democrat who made totalitarian democracy possible. Opposite to liberals, argued Talmon, Rousseau did not consider politics ‘to be a matter of trial and error’. Rousseauian vision of politics, based on the idea that ‘*La volonté générale est toujours droite* [the general will is always upright]’, offered a new ideal that became essential for totalitarian democracy — that there is a ‘sole and exclusive truth in politics’. Hence, Rousseau’s ‘lawgiver’ (*legislateur*) was interpreted by Talmon all too similar to George Orwell’s ‘Big Brother’ and Stalin’s ‘engineers of the human soul’. It was the idea of *volonté générale* in particular, Talmon believed, that became ‘the driving force of totalitarian democracy’” (131). See also Das, who maintains that “Talmon traced the roots of modern totalitarianism to Rousseau” (555), and Seitschek, who writes that „Rousseau nimmt eine zentrale Rolle in Talmons Denken ein, da ihn Talmon — sehr eigenwillig — als direkten Vorläufer des Totalitarismus interpretiert“ (57).

⁷ This position can be thought of in relation to Jonathan Marks’ consideration of the role of “disharmony” in attempted resolutions of human consciousness. Marks points out that people are born without the “sentiment of existence,” since at birth we lack “self-consciousness,” which depends for its existence on memory. He suggests that Rousseau’s savage differs from the “sociable man” because the sociable man exists “always outside himself,” while the savage “lives in himself.” These tensions within the individual lead Marks to claim that “Rousseau views the human good not as a unity but as a set of disharmonious attributes or tendencies that must somehow be arranged in a life so as not to tear the human being apart” (86-87). Projected onto the political sphere, Marks suggests that “Rousseau was willing to preserve tension in order to give the plurality of human goods their due” and “made the savage nation, a nation characterized by struggle, a pattern for his visions of the good life” (88). Marks specifically contrasts this perspective with the one Talmon presents, in which (he claims) Rousseau’s “totalitarian” tendencies are linked directly to Rousseau’s (perceived) neurotic character. As Marks puts it, “to call someone who [like Rousseau] favored civic education and civil religion a totalitarian is to empty that term of its moral seriousness” (87).

⁸ These definitions come from a 2 December 2013 blogpost by Dennis Loo, author of *Globalization and the Demolition of Society*, on a site dedicated to discussion of this book. Similar insights into the distinction of individuality from individualism can be found at the Emerson Post blogsite, dedicated to discussion of the works of Ralph Waldo Emerson, where on 9 December 2009 “Mr. Morris” commented, “Individuality as I see it is about the expression of self; an expression of mind and spirit; an expression of your thoughts and those things that make you a unique being worthy of notoriety. Individualism is the spirit that sees the world and life (to use an economic term) as a zero

sum game. The idea that one person's win is another person's lost [*sic*] or that one's happiness may require another's grief. The idea that someone necessarily has to get the short end of the stick in the 'game' of life...." See finally John Horvat's comments in *Return to Order*, a book dedicated to the establishment of an organic Christian community, in which Horvat states, "We make a distinction between individuality and individualism. Man manifests his individuality when he fully develops his personality and talents by which he is different from others. At the same time, individuality encourages man to develop his intensely social character by participating in life together in community, acknowledging a moral law, and promoting the common good. The more specific, richer, and stronger this personal life, the more intense the social life. Thus, individuality results in stronger community." Meanwhile, for Horvat, "Individualism is a deformation of individuality by which man makes himself the center of an enclosed world of personal self-interest that tends to disregard the social character of man and his role in community" (74). One might ask if these tendencies to establish an opposition between individuality and individualism are supplanting the earlier emphasis on the opposition between individualism and conformism that prevailed during the Cold War period.

References

- Babbitt, Irving. *Rousseau and Romanticism*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin, 1919.
- Barney, Joseph Aldo. *The Educational Ideas of Irving Babbitt — Critical Humanism and American Higher Education*. Dissertation presented at Loyola University, Chicago, 1974.
- Coffman, Michael. *Rescuing a Broken America: Why America is Deeply Divided and How to Heal it Constitutionally*. Garden City, NY: Morgan James, 2010.
- Crocker, Lester G. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau: The Prophetic Voice*. 2 vols. New York: Macmillan, 1973.
- . "Professor Babbitt Revisited." *Studies in Romanticism* 10.4 (Fall 1971): 260-282.
- Cunningham, Craig A. *Rousseau's Influence on American Education*, 25 April 2013, www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lu6xh4MJIOs. Accessed 13 April 2018
- Dame, Frederick William. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau in American Literature: Traces, Influence, Transformation 1760-1860: A Paradigm of French-German Culture Emanation in America*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang, 1996.
- Das, Frank Thakur. "Review Article: The Enigmatic Rousseau." *Indian Journal of Political Science* 32.4 (October-December 1971): 551-561.
- Davis, Glenn A. "Irving Babbitt, the Moral Imagination, and Progressive Education." *Humanitas* 19.1-2 (2006): 50-64.
- Dubnov, Arie. "Priest or Jester? Jacob L. Talmon (1916-1980) on History and Intellectual Engagement." *History of European Ideas* 34 (2008): 133-145.
- English, Andrea R. *Discontinuity in Learning: Dewey, Herbart, and Education as Transformation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- Fabre, Jean. "Le Jean-Jacques Rousseau de Lester G. Crocker." *Revue d'Histoire littéraire de la France* 75.5 (September-October 1975): 799-826.
- Fuller, Timothy. "The Complementarity of Political Philosophy and Liberal Education in the Thought of Leo Strauss." *The Cambridge Companion to Leo Strauss*. Ed. Steven B. Smith. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009. 241-262.
- Hoeverler, J. David, Jr. "Babbitt and Contemporary Conservative Thought in America." *Modern Age* Spring/Summer 1984: 181-192.

- Horvat, John, II. *Return to Order: From a Frenzied Economy to an Organic Christian Society: Where We've Been, How We Got Here, and Where We Need to Go*. York, PA: York Press, 2013.
- Israel, Jonathan I. *Democratic Enlightenment: Philosophy, Revolution, and Human Rights 1750-1790*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011.
- . *Radical Enlightenment: Philosophy and the Making of Modernity 1650-1750*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001.
- . *Revolution of the Mind: Radical Enlightenment and the Intellectual Origins of Modern Democracy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2010.
- Jeffries, Judson L. *Huey P. Newton: The Radical Theorist*. Jackson: University Press of Mississippi, 2002.
- Koons, Robert C. "The War of the Three Humanisms: Irving Babbitt and the Recovery of Classical Learning." *Modern Age* 52.3 (Summer 2010): 198-207.
- Loo, Dennis. "Individualism vs. Individuality." DennisLoo.com. 2 December 2013, dennisloo.com/Articles/individuality-v-individualism.html. Accessed 14 February 2018.
- Marks, Jonathan. *Perfection and Disharmony in the Thought of Jean-Jacques Rousseau*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005.
- Masters, Roger D. *The Political Philosophy of Rousseau*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1968.
- Mattson, Kevin. *Intellectuals in Action: The Origins of the New Left and Radical Liberalism, 1945-1970*. University Park, PA: Pennsylvania State University Press, 2002.
- Meyer, Adolphe Erich, and Robert Frederic Lawson. "Higher Education." *The Educational Awakening. Education*. Encyclopedia Britannica Online. 31 January 2018, www.britannica.com/print/article/179408. Accessed 12 April 2018.
- "Mr. Morris: The BK Good Guy." "Individualism vs. Individuality." *The Emerson Post: A Brooklyn Good Guys Reporting*. 9 December 2009, theemersonpost.wordpress.com/2009/12/09/individuality-vs-individualism/. Accessed 14 February 2018.
- Riley, Patrick. "A Possible Explanation of Rousseau's General Will." *The American Political Science Review* 64.1 (March 1970): 86-97.

- . "Rousseau's Philosophy of Transformative, 'Denaturing' Education." *Oxford Review of Education* 37.5 (October 2011): 573-586.
- Rousseau, Jean-Jacques. "To M. de Malesherbes, 26 January 1762." *The Confessions, Including the Letters to Malesherbes*. Tr. Christopher Kelly. Collected Works of Rousseau 5. Ed. Christopher Kelly, Roger D. Masters, and Peter G. Stillman. Hanover, CT: Dartmouth College/University Press of New England, 1995. 574-577.
- . "Discourse on Political Economy." *The Social Contract and Other Later Political Writings*. Trans. and ed. Victor Gourevitch. Cambridge Texts in the History of Political Thought. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997. 3-38.
- Seitschek, Hans Otto. *Politischer Messianismus: Totalitarismuskritik und philosophische Geschichtsschreibung im Anschluß an Jacob Leib Talmon*. Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh, 2005.
- Shklar, Judith N. *Men and Citizens: A Study of Rousseau's Social Theory*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1969.
- . "Rousseau's Images of Authority." *American Political Science Review* 58.4 (December 1964): 919-932.
- Somr, Miroslav, and Lenka Hrušková. "Herbart's Philosophy of Pedagogy and Educational Teaching (The Views and Differences of Opinion) [Herbertowska filozofia pedagogiki i kształcenia]." *Studia Edukacyjne* 33 (2014): 413-429.
- Spurlin, Paul M. *Rousseau in America, 1760-1809*. University, AL: University of Alabama Press, 1969.
- Strauss, Leo. "On the Intentions of Rousseau." *Social Research* 41.4 (December 1947): 455-487.
- Talmon, J. L. *The Rise of Totalitarian Democracy*. Boston: Beacon, 1952.
- Wisconsin Historical Society. "America's First Kindergarten Teacher: A Brief Biography of Margarethe Schurz." *Wisconsin Historical Society*, 1996-2007, www.wisconsinhistory.org/Records/Article/CS4835. Accessed 5 February 2018.
- Wright, Johnson Kent. "Jonathan Israel, *Democratic Enlightenment: Philosophy, Revolution and Human Rights 1750-1790*. Oxford: Oxford UP, 2011 [Review]." *H-France Forum* 9:1 (Winter 2014): 1-25, www.hfrance.net/forum/forumvol9/Israel1.pdf. Accessed 9 Feb. 2014.